

EFFECTS OF WRITING ANXIETY AND WRITING SELF-REGULATION ON ENGLISH WRITING MOTIVATION AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract

The aim of this current study is to find out the Effect of Writing anxiety and writing self-regulation on English writing Motivation and Academic Achievement of Secondary School Students. A quantitative research design, particularly survey research design was used to examine the aforementioned effects. 50 Secondary School students are the sample of the study from Hazara division enrolled in 10th class from BISE Abbottabad. Four instruments: three questionnaires, namely, writing Anxiety questionnaire, by Cheng, 2004, SRQ (Self-regulation Questionnaire), Academic Writing Motivation Questionnaire AWMQ and Achievement of students in terms of obtained marks in 9th class were used for data collection. The results of the study showed that students writing motivation had significantly effect of both the writing anxiety and writing self-regulation. The findings further indicated that students' was significantly affected by writing self-regulation. It is suggested in the study that all these factors must be kept in mind in the time of teaching and instruction process of English writing process. It would facilitate the teaching and learning process of English writing. Thus the academic achievement of the students would be improved.

Keywords: Effect, writing anxiety, writing self-regulation, English writing motivation, and academic achievement

INTRODUCTION

Writing i.e., English writing is a complex and difficult process especially for numerous ESL (English as a second language) and EFL (English as a foreign language) i.e. for foreigner authors due to its complex nature and their less vocabulary. They are weak in English grammar and have less vocab which resultantly hampers their writing ability in English. Thus, ESL and EFL students have less knowledge of English which adversely affect their writing process; hence they are unable to write English in effective manner in comparison with 1st language specially mother tongue. In 1st language the writers have an easy and fast approach and as they know all the basic hints and tips of the language thus, they can write more easily and effectively means they can easily express themselves. Zailaini et al. (2015), considers it as a difficult job more specifically for students from EFL and ESL background. From Middle ESTERN countries so many of the students of Arabia having ESL background have many problems, issues and hindrances to obtain the necessary

skills of language especially of foreign language skills of listening, reading, speaking and more certainly of writing. When EFL students want to learn English writing skills and want to become masters and experts in it, the difficult and complex nature of English creates high anxiety level in them, which discourage the to complete their writing job hence they want to leave this assigned job i.e., practice of Writing in English. Resultantly less achievement on the part of them (Cohyono, 2023). So, as the students find it rather difficult and complex job their writing anxiety, self-confidence, writing self-regulation and writing-motivation become low which adversely affect their performance and achievement and thus ultimately hinder their writing performance. All such types of issues are the result of less practice and low experience in English writing (Mason & Merga (2022). Same kind of issues are also seen for students having EFL background, as they have less interaction with the use of English i.e., writing in English. Sabti (2019) said that many of EFL students are less competence in English writing more especially academic writing skills. English is only limited to EFL class room environment and settings in Pakistan where teachers are mostly native speakers of Urdu, hence resultantly formal English leaning in class room is only to limited extent and it is only possible for our native learners to learn only very limited and basic reading, listening, speaking and most certainly writing skills of English language, as submitted by (Al-Nafjan and Alhawsawi, 2022), is that one field of linguistic where many mistakes are committed by secondary school students” (p. 4). 2nd language learners may have several hurdles and hindrances when they write in English, for example such as “misapplication of some words, parallelism, repetition, and length and structure of sentence, deficiency of varieties and misappropriation of certain cohesive devices and tools” (Ahmad, 2022). All these hurdles and hindrances are in grammar and also in the choice of words in sentences. Problems and issues are not only in ideas organization but in fluency and conventions too. All these complications adversely affect the student's quality of writing at all. If the students are interested in learning writing and carry on trying for its improvement, they can easily overcome all such hurdles. This research has found out that writing self-regulation and writing motivation are directly related with improvement and development of writing ability. The past published works associated with the current topic showed that such type of aspects are associated to the improvement of EFL writing ability and achievement (Chea & Shumow, 2017; Kırmızı & Kırmızı, 2015). As writing ability of students is not directly enhanced by these factors, these help the students and inspire them to work hard and make progress greater to improve writing ability (Patra, 2022). On students' achievement and performance such aspects put positive effects. Writing with anxiety, self-regulation and motivation is studied and examined in EFL and ESL contexts Torres and Alieto (2019). So far however hardly there any study in the world has been conducted with one student, which has examined these variables in one study. In the literature of this study this gap is addressed in the literature of this study. The relationship of writing self-regulation and writing anxiety is focused with respect to writing motivation and academic achievement among EFL secondary school students (learners). It looked essential to study in detail differences in individuals in writing anxiety, writing self-regulation, writing motivation and academic achievement and their relationship too in EFL settings. Thus the aim of this study is to

find and identify the levels of writing self-regulation, writing anxiety, writing motivation and academic achievement of SSC secondary school students.

LITERATURE REVIEW

• In various studies factors i.e. affective ones, for example academic achievement, English writing motivation, self-regulation and writing anxiety, perform play an important and significant role in influencing EFL writing. Several academics and studies showed that less confidence, lack of motivation, self-regulation and academic achievement, have negative influence upon EFL writing performance (Li et al., 2022). These studies most of the time confirmed that self-regulation in writing can improve writing motivation and writing performance greatly, while writing motivation, writing ability and academic achievement of the students are highly and negatively influenced by writing anxiety. Such factors play an important and vital role in shaping the attitude and behavior of students' resultantly good or bad performance or achievement occurs. It is considered by many researchers that anxiety is a main factor which greatly influence academic performance (Cruz et al., 2022). It is particularly and specially found that anxiety badly affected the writing of L1 learners (Kurniasih et al., 2022), for example, identified that "anxiety as the main aspect which is the cause the weakening of students' academic achievement in the EFL/ESL contexts" (p. 208). Further anxiety is connected with many other factors, features and elements for example writing self-regulation, writing motivation and students' behaviors and attitude too towards writing (Sabti et al., 2019). Alimorad and Adib (2022), for example, emphasize that "anxiety discourages and demotivates the students and in response there grow negative behavior and self-regulation on the part of them towards writing" (p. 57). It is further stated that anxiety is considered harmful for students' writing performance, e.g. the Arab EFL context. Anxiety is defined as a student's or learner's feelings of nervousness, uneasiness, fears, worries, and other physiological reactions when doing a certain work for certain language skills for example reading, writing or speaking (Pabro-Maquidato, 2021). Anxiety in writing, Wang et al, (2023) have defined it as "the trend and thinking of a person to refrain and abstain from the writing process when it is assessed in some way or the other" (p. 181). As a situational aspect anxiety is however defined in the present study which is connected with the feelings of worry and rumination side by side responses to the active perspiration, beating of heart and negative expectations and the bad attitude of a students' knowledge when doing a special assigned writing work at time and place constraint. The bad attitudes are defined as less confidence when an individual understand the mistakes they do as a hint of incapability and sense of anxiety that compelled them to withdraw their struggles and effort and evade trial, which resultantly weaken and underestimate the standardize quality of the instructional process and performance of students. EFL writing is affected by many other factors as well as motivation, self-regulation, all these play an important role in EFL writing performance ,specially in learning English in the EFL context in general (Teng, 2021). Many studies indicated that writing performance of students and their outcomes are positively inter related with academic achievement, writing motivation, self-regulation in an academic setting (Hong et al., 2021). It is quite important that students and learners must be made aware that all these factors i.e. writing self-

regulation, writing motivation, achievement and self-efficacy, these greatly put influence on their willingness to complete a work related with English writing. In the current study achievement and writing motivation. In this study, writing motivation and achievement is stated as ones wish to do with satisfaction to satisfactorily to have an internal feeling of private success (E Quispe-Bendezú et al., 2020). Motivation of writing is an important factor and aspect for ones achievements in academics. A by tan et al, (2023) showed that an individual's academic performance has positive relationship with motivation This concept and opinion is fully recommended by by Kaya and Ercag, (2023) who described that academic performance is positively and significantly affected by motivation. In short we can conclude that motivation is a powerful and an active indicator for one's performance (Lavrijsen, 2022). A study conducted by Wang (2023) on these factors such as achievement, motivation and self-regulation showed that high levels of all these factors most of the time motivate learners to do great struggle to a work that may complete their objectives. This study also study self-efficacy and self-regulation and these are considered as beliefs Of individuals about their abilities that play an important role in excite ones attitude (Bandura, 2026). These factor play a vaster role and powerful prediction on the behavior of an individual. Three is a dire need of powerful confidence strong motivation for a writing work. A learner having all these factors in powerful and strong category may have more interest in making efforts to do a writing work (Schunk, 2023) An individual can be driven by High self-efficacy, self –regulation, to determine huger determination when facing difficult situations when completing a written work.. A study conducted by Bai and Wang (2023) stated that among all the motivational constructs self-efficacy, self-regulation are often stronger predictor. Thus, these can play a main, vital and principal role in shaping writing performance and achievement of students. Another study, by Ghazali, (2011), on 120 Malaysian ESL students, showed that a moderate low level of these factors showed a moderate parallel writing performance. It is further stated that individuals with weak and low level of self-regulation self-efficacy and motivation do small efforts in doing a task. On the other hand individuls with high level of these factors do strong struggle and found new solutions for problems and issues in time of facing difficulties (Bachrach, 2022). In a nut shell all these factors are strong and positive role and prediction in ones' success doing a special written work.

METHODS

Research Design

In the study a survey research design was used. The purpose of the use of this survey research design is to measure the effect of given variables (Headley et al., 2020). In short, this research study seeks to measure the effect among given variables. On the basis of this, i.e. this research design, the present study studies the effect of writing anxiety, writing self-regulation on writing motivation, and academic achievement of secondary school students. Five point Likert scale questionnaires were used in the study to measure the factors of writing anxiety, writing self-regulation and writing motivation

INSTRUMENTATION AND DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURES

2.1.1 Data were collected through four instruments, i.e. questionnaires, namely, writing Anxiety questionnaire, by Cheng, 2004, SRQ (Self-regulation Questionnaire), Academic Writing Motivation Questionnaire AWMQ and Academic Achievement of students in terms of obtained marks in 9th class Annual Exam, 2022 from BISE Abbottabad.

2.1.2 PARTICIPANTS

Based on Krejcie and Morgan sample size table the sample of the study comprised of 50 Secondary School from Hazara division

DATA ANALYSIS

Analysis used inferential statistics, namely, regression. Though, the analysis was used firstly to find out whether there is significant effect in writing performance across the levels for each factor, namely, writing anxiety, writing self-regulation, writing motivation, and academic achievement, and the latter examines aforementioned factors.

Table 4.1: Effect of Writing anxiety and writing self-regulation on academic writing motivation of students

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.006	.021		.304	.762
Writing Anxiety	.040	.063	.032	.629	.530
Writing-self-regulation	1.027	.054	.961	18.938	.000
R= .992 ^a	R ² =.984	Adj. R ² = .984	5111.47	0.000	

Table 4.1 shows that the R value 0.992 that reflect overall writing self-regulation has significant effect on writing motivation. The value of R² is 0.984 that reflects 9.84% of the variability in writing motivation.is explained by overall writing anxiety and writing self-regulation. The F=5111.47 and the sig=000 that indicates statistically significant and correct predication between the variables at p=0.05 significance level. The value of β (slop of coefficient) for overall anxiety .040 reflects that writing motivation varies positively with the change in overall anxiety and t value .032 is statistically significant $\alpha =000$. Therefore, it is calculated that the overall writing anxiety and writing self-regulation positively influence the writing motivation.

Table 4.2: Effect of anxiety and writing self-regulation on academic achievement of students

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	108.965	4.094		26.617	.000
Writing Anxiety	-.433	12.314	-.007	-.035	.972
Writing SR	44.145	10.543	.865	4.187	.000
R=.858	R ² =.736	Adj. R ² =.733	229.91	0.000	

Table 4.2 shows that the R value 0.858 that reflect overall writing self-regulation has significant effect on academic achievement. The value of R² is 0.736 that reflects 7.36%

of the variability in academic achievement is explained by overall writing anxiety and writing self-regulation. The $F=229.91$ and the $\text{sig}=0.000$ that indicates statistically significant and correct predication between the variables at $p=0.05$ significance level. The value of β (slope of coefficient) for overall anxiety 26.617 reflects that academic achievement varies positively with the change in overall anxiety and t value .007 is statistically significant $\alpha =0.000$. Therefore, it is calculated that over all writing anxiety and writing self-regulation positively influence the academic achievement.

DISCUSSION

The aim of this study is to find out the effect of writing anxiety, writing self-regulation on English writing motivation and academic achievements of secondary school students. Further, the levels of writing anxiety writing self-regulation, writing motivation and academic achievements of secondary school students are too indicated by this study. The findings of this study show that that secondary school students having high level of anxiety in English writing process show unsatisfactory results in writing performance and academic achievement of secondary school students. Due to high level of anxiety secondary school students usually avoid in writing in English and this can adversely affect their performance in writing as well as in academics achievement. Thus the students do not take active part in English writing and try to refrain from taking part in writing process of English language. They usually believe that it is for better for them not to take part in English writing process to avoid the negative remarks and impression of others and their class fellows too about their writing abilities. They usually lack confidence in their writing abilities. They do not enjoy writing practices. They tried their best to avoid situations that have the demand of writing in English from them. Theory says that high of writing anxiety regularly hampers the situation and takes the students to a disappointing achievement and performance, and students having low level of anxiety are considered to obtained better results in writing tests (Atay & Kurt, 2006; Erkan & Saban, 2011; Pajares, 2003; Senko, 2016). Further we can say that learners with high anxiety level do not try to reach to a writing task as they consider it as dangerous threat as well as challenge and thus they would not make struggles to improve their performance especially in English writing. The recommendations from the results of the study are the students with high level of anxiety having low and poor performance in writing while students with low level of anxiety have good academic achievement and writing performance. The results and findings of the study match fully to those of Erkan and Saban's (2011) study, which confirmed that the performance of the students will be poor and low having high anxiety level and performance of the students will be better having moderate and low level of anxiety. As for writing self-regulation and writing motivation are concerned the study indicates that many of the school students have low level in these. This shows that due to pressure of time, lack of special practice in English writing, negative elevation guided secondary school students to have moderate level of these factors. The finding indicates that negative elevation of teachers , time pressure, less English writing practice are as the most vital and central components that decrease the students' writing motivation and writing self-regulation and resultantly cause their anxiety in writing (Elias et al., 2010; Kırmızı & Kırmızı, 2015). It is also indicated by the findings of this study most of the

secondary school students with low academic achievement and motivation in writing are not intended to work hard. As they unwillingly face difficulties and challenges which cause great hindrances in achieving targets they want to get and achieve. The secondary school students have adverse effects and beliefs upon them and thus always think negatively with disappointment. Surely and certainly this goes against the postulate of the academic achievement theory that the students with high level of academic achievement and motivation in writing have positive beliefs in themselves and well orientation with self-confidence and get their goals with positive efforts (Elias et al., 2010; Maehr & Zusho, 2009; Senko, 2016). People having low level of self-regulation can cause anxiety, rumination and worry and also stress that leads them negative attitudes. This is similar with the opinion that “people with low self-regulation may believe that things are more difficult than they really are—a belief that can foster anxiety and stress and leave few choices for how to solve problems” (Schunk & DiBenedetto, 2016, p. 37). Resultantly low self-regulation in writing leads to not satisfactory writing performance and academic achievement of secondary school students.

CONCLUSION

Writing skill is considered as emotional and cognitive activity too that is why it is strongly connected with effective factors i.e. anxiety, writing motivation and writing self-regulation. The findings and results of the study focuses and put stress that these effective factors of English as a foreign language learning i.e. EFL learning might be encouraged. The study give suggestions that for minimizing anxiety for learners the teachers as well as peers should give positive feedback in writing process to a certain extent. A study was conducted in this connection by Atay and Kurt (2006) the study provided report that review of peers in writing process has positive and suitable good results and effects on ESL English as a Second Language Learners writing anxiety. The teachers should minimize their students' anxiety in learning by helping the review process of peers. It is indicated by the findings of the study that the students with high level of self-regulation in writings always show unsatisfactory writing performance. However, the social cognitive theory of Bandura (1986), states that the factors i.e. self-regulation factor is a significant and important positive predictor for students' academic performance. Bandura (1997) stated that the beliefs of self-regulation are mainly recognized by enactive achievement that individual and individuals can gain self-confidence upon struggling and fulfilling works. When one is able to obtain success resultantly his self-confidence increases which becomes the cause of his consistent success and positive performance frequently while ones failure whereas self-confidence is usually reduces. There are limitations of the study, i.e. gender has not been studied due to unequal strength of male and female students. To fulfill this gap future research should therefore, study and examine differences in genders writing anxiety, writing self-regulation, academic achievement and writing motivation and performance toward EFL context. As this research study only focused on EFL secondary school students hence, the results and findings can't be generalized to EFL students at other levels of education.

Writing anxiety can have a significant impact on writing motivation. When individuals experience writing anxiety, they may feel a sense of fear, stress, or apprehension about

the writing process. This can lead to a decrease in their motivation to write and, in some cases, even avoidance of writing tasks altogether. Writing anxiety can be caused by various factors, such as fear of judgment, perfectionism, lack of confidence in one's writing abilities, or past negative experiences with writing. Here are some recommendations to address writing anxiety and boost writing motivation:

RECOMMENDATIONS

On the basis of conclusions, following recommendations can be formulated:

1. It is recommended that the students should be helped through counseling that writing anxiety is a normal feeling and can be overcome by mindfulness-based and cognitive behavioral interventions of parents and teachers. In these interventions the students should be encouraged to question their own thinking patterns. They are encouraged to imagine the reality without distortions caused by stressful events and lastly, they are encouraged to change their thoughts positively and improve their self-regulation.
2. Since anxiety has profound impact on academic achievement of the students, it is necessary to help out the secondary school students to reduce test anxiety through group work among students.

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